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Chemical evolution models of the Galaxy

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Abstract

We discuss the chemical evolution of the Milky Way in the light of state-of-the-art theoretical models of Galaxy formation and evolution. Currently, we are in a golden era for this field of research thanks to the advent of large spectroscopic Galactic surveys and projects, which are enhanced by the advent of ESA Gaia mission. In this way, detailed stellar abundances of stars Milky Way can be obtained. Then, by means of detailed Galactic chemical evolution models, it is possible to predict the chemical abundances expected in the stars of each Galactic component: halo, thick disc, thin disc and bulge. In particular, here we focus on the interpretation of the chemical bimodality between the Galactic thick and thin discs, and discuss applications to various abundance patterns.

1 Introduction

The goal of Galactic archaeology is to understand the formation and evolution of galaxies with particular focus on our Galaxy, from abundance patterns and stellar ages. We are in a period of great advances for this field of research thanks to the advent of large spectroscopic Galactic surveys, see for example APOGEE (Majewski et al. 2017), Gaia-ESO (Gilmore et al. 2012) and GALAH (Zucker et al. 2012) among others. The role of these projects is then enhanced by the advent of the ESA Gaia mission, which has provided its third data release with a comprehensive chemical cartography of the Milky Way (Recio-Blanco et al. 2023). In this way, detailed chemical abundances of stars in the Milky Way can be obtained. Then, by means of detailed Galactic chemical evolution models, it is possible to predict the chemical abundances expected in the stars of each Galactic component (halo, thick disc, thin disc and bulge). From the comparison between observational data and theoretical model predictions, we can then reconstruct the history of star formation occurred in each component, and thus the history of the entire Galaxy. In the literature, several Galactic chemical evolution models have been proposed to explain the chemical evolution of the Milky Way (see Matteucci 2021 for a review). In particular, recent observations found two distinct chemical sequences in the $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ vs $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ diagram of Milky Way stars corresponding to the Galactic thick and thin discs (Hayden et al. 2015; Mikolaitis et al. 2017). The origin of such bimodality is still a matter of debate in Galactic archaeology and different scenarios have been proposed to explain it.

Figure 1: Predicted and observed $[Mg/Fe]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$ in the solar vicinity in the framework of the parallel model. The data are from the AMBRE Project (Mikolaitis et al. 2017): thin disc (green), thick disc (magenta) and metal-rich high- α (MRHA, grey). The predictions are from the parallel model for the thick disc (dashed black line) and the thin disc (continuous black line).

In particular, in this contribution I discuss the parallel model developed by Grisoni et al. (2017) to follow separately the evolution in the Galactic thick and thin discs, and its applications. Finally, I outline future perspectives of this work.

2 Results

In Fig. 1, we show the observed and predicted $[Mg/Fe]$ vs. $[Fe/H]$ in the solar vicinity: the data are from the AMBRE Project (Mikolaitis et al. 2017) and it is possible to see the two sequences corresponding to the thick and thin discs, with the thick-disc stars having higher $[\alpha/Fe]$ values with respect to the thin disc. The data are then compared with the predictions of the parallel model (Grisoni et al. 2017). In the parallel approach, the metal-rich high- α (MRHA) stars can be interpreted as metal-rich thick disc stars. On the other hand, the two-infall approach cannot fit these stars: in this framework, they can be explained by stellar migration from the inner disc. The parallel model developed in Grisoni et al. (2017) has been then extended also to the other Galactocentric distances in Grisoni et al. (2018), where they studied abundance gradients along the disc. The model has been then applied also to various chemical elements, from the light ones (Grisoni et al. 2019) up to the heaviest ones (Grisoni et al. 2020). It has been applied also to CNO elements, see e.g. results for carbon (Romano et al. 2020) and nitrogen (Grisoni et al. 2021). New data also for precise stellar ages and detailed star formation histories can be fundamental to further constrain the relative timescales and formation scenarios of the Galactic thick and thin discs (Grisoni et al. submitted). Moreover, we discuss new insights on the chemical evolution of the Milky Way that can be given also by zoom-in cosmological simulations of galaxy formation (in preparation).

3 Conclusions and future perspectives

We are in a golden era for Galactic archaeology thanks to the advent of large spectroscopic surveys and projects which are boosting the number of questions that need to be solved by theoretical models. In this context, we have discussed the chemical evolution of the Milky Way by means of detailed Galactic chemical evolution models. In particular, the parallel model is a powerful tool to follow the chemical evolution of the Galactic thick and thin discs. New data also for stellar ages and star formation histories can be fundamental to further constrain the relative timescales of formation of these Galactic components (Grisoni et al. submitted). Moreover, cosmological simulations can give further insights about the chemical evolution of Milky Way-like galaxies.

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